

Meiotic chromosomes of male green leafhoppers (GLH)

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We studied the meiotic chromosomes of GLH *Nephotettix virescens*. Newly emerged, insectary-reared GLH males were fixed in Carnoy's fluid for 24 h. Later, their testes were macerated on glass slides with a drop of 2% lacto-aceto-orcein and 45% acetic acid. Chromosome examinations showed that GLH spermatogonia divided mitotically and spermatocytal processes followed the conventional reduc-

1. Chromosomes of male *N. virescens* at diakinesis showing $2n=15$ (7IIA+XO). The sex chromosome is indicated by an arrow. Magnification, 1500X (oil immersion). IRRI, 1984.

2. *N. virescens* pachytene chromosomes comprising autosomes, chromosome with nucleolar organizing region (NOR), and sex chromosome and idiogram showing the relative mean lengths. Sex chromosome is indicated by an arrow. Magnification, 1500X (oil immersion). IRRI, 1984.

tional-equational meiotic divisions. The primary spermatocytes at diakinesis (Fig. 1) had 7 bivalent autosomes and a univalent X-chromosome making the genomic complement $2n=15$ (7IIA + XO).

At pachytene (Fig. 2), relative mean chromosome length was 0.074-0.189. The sex chromosome measured 0.083 and the autosome with the nucleolar organizing region (NOR) had a relative mean length of 0.153. These chromosomes condensed maximally during premetaphase into

dumbbells of bivalents measuring as follows: 4, 3, 3, 2.5, 2.5, 2.5, 1.9, and 1. The sex chromosome measured 1μ while the chromosome with NOR measured 3μ .

The insemination potential of male GLH as determined by the mean meiotic index was approximated to be 0.84.

Spontaneous chromosomal aberrations in individual GLH included 0.77% hypoploidy or reduction in chromosome number and 0.47% agmatoploidy or increase in number. □

Host plants of rice leafhopper (LF)

Marasmia patnalis Bradley

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Simultaneous damage to rice leaves by two LF species, *Marasmia patnalis* Bradley and *Chaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée, was observed on the IRRI experimental farm from Oct 1983 to Mar 1984. *C. medinalis* commonly feeds on alternative hosts, but no information is available on the ability of *M. patnalis* to survive rice-free periods on alternative hosts. We tested *M. patnalis* survival on nine rice-field weeds (see table) in a no-choice trial

Weeds tested as host plants to the LF *M. patnalis*,^a IRRI, 1984.

Family, plant ^b	Survival from 1st instar to pupa ^c (%)	Remarks on feeding of larvae
Poaceae (Gramineae)		
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	48 a	Severe scraping
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i>	14 b	High scraping
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i>	4 bc	Low scraping
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	0 c	Scraping was observed, but larvae did not live to pupate.
Cyperaceae		
<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	2 c	Two adjacent leaves near the tip of the inflorescence were folded.

^aTen replications/plant species, 5 larvae/plant. ^bIdentified by R. T. Lubigan, IRRI. ^cMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05) by Duncan's multiple range test. There was no survival on *Fimbristylis littoralis*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Ipomoea aquatica*, and *Sphenoclea zeylanica*.

under greenhouse conditions. Individually caged test plants were infested with newly hatched 1st-instar larvae from a *M. patnalis* greenhouse colony.

M. patnalis survived on four of the

weed species. Survival was highest (48%) on *Leersia hexandra*, with a 17-d larval period. *Echinochloa colona* leaves were scraped, but the larvae did not live to pupate. Survival was poor and larval

period extended (25 d) on *Cyperus difformis*, which may cause the larvae to migrate to the young transplanted rice crop early in the growing season. □

Rice whorl maggot (RWM) effect on yield loss

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RWM usually attacks irrigated rice plants and retards their growth from seedbed stage to about 40 d after transplanting (DT). In hot, lowland conditions in the Philippines, plants usually recover from RWM damage, and exhibit no yield loss even with heavy infestation. However, scientists suspect there has been some yield loss from RWM in the IRRI maximum yield trials (MYT). We evaluated the effect of RWM damage with 2 insecticide treatments on 10 cultivars or lines planted in the MYT (Table 1) in Mar-Jul 1984.

RWM damage ranged from 1.8 to 6.5% in the insecticide-treated plots and 11.4 to

43.5% in check plots (Table 2). The correlation coefficient between RWM damage and yield loss was 0.57 ($n = 10$) and not significant, indicating that RWM infestation at the levels in this study did not affect yield.

Similarly, percent deadhearts caused by stem borers in early stages did not significantly correlate with yield loss ($r = 0.02$). In contrast, percent of tungro-infected plants was highly correlated with yield loss ($r = 0.98^{**}$). □

Table 1. Insecticide treatments.

Wk after transplanting	Highly protected	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Check	Rate (kg ai/ha)
1	Diazinon 5G and monocrotophos	1.0 + 1.5		
2	Deltamethrin 2.5EC	0.0125		
3	Diazinon 5G and carbaryl 85WP	1.0 + 1.5		
4	Acephate 75SP	0.75		
5	MIPC 50WP	0.75		
6	Monocrotophos 30EC	0.75	Monocrotophos 30EC	0.75
7	Acephate 75SP	0.75	Acephate 75SP	0.75
8	Diazinon 20EC	0.75	Diazinon 20EC	0.75
11	Acephate 75SP	0.75	Acephate 75SP	0.75

Table 2. Effect of RWM infestation on the yield of 10 rice varieties and lines used in the IRRI MYT.^a

Cultivar/line	RWM damaged leaves (%) on 20 hills/plot		Deadhearts (%) on 160 hills/plot		Hills (%) with tungro virus disease on 160 hills/plot, 40 DT ^d		Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Highly protected ^b	Check ^c	Highly protected	Check	Highly protected	Check	Highly protected	Check
IR5 8	3.40 bcd	18.82 abc	1.14 bc	0.56 ab	0.00 a	0.00 a	3.73 b	3.38 b
IR31847-67-2-1-1-2	2.65 bc	29.75 c	1.38 bc	0.64 ab	0.00 a	0.00 a	4.36 b	4.50 c
IR36	2.64 abcd	27.39 c	2.66 d	0.38 ab	2.03 a	42.65 b	4.20 b	2.20 ab
IE29725-3-1-3-2	3.10 bcd	27.39 c	1.28 bc	0.52 ab	0.00 a	0.00 a	3.78 b	4.10 c
IR31851-6-3-3-3-2	4.09 cd	15.22 ab	0.47 a	0.43 ab	0.16 a	0.00 a	4.53 b	4.26 c
IR8	6.48 d	40.52 cd	0.00 a	0.00 a	100.00 c	97.50 c	0.00 a	0.00 a
IR42	3.31 bcd	43.58 d	0.64 ab	0.00 a	13.03 b	93.75 c	3.45 b	0.00 a
IR21840-154-3-2-2-3	1.81 a	11.43 a	1.34 bc	0.64 ab	0.00 a	0.00 a	3.41 b	3.85 c
IR29723-143-3-2-1	1.89 b	25.08 c	1.67 cd	0.91 b	0.00 a	0.00 a	4.51 b	4.97 abcd
IR25587-133-3-2-2-2	3.00 bc	21.06 bc	1.20 bc	1.16 b	0.00 a	0.00 a	3.61 b	3.37 b

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bHighly protected from 1 wk to 11 wk after transplanting. ^cProtected only after 6 wk to 11 wk after transplanting. ^dDays after transplanting.

Sensitivity levels of green leafhopper (GLH) populations to insecticides at IRRI in 1983-84

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We suspected that GLH at IRRI were

becoming less sensitive or resistant to insecticides because of frequent application. GLH were collected from tungro-infected IR22 in Dec 1983 and reared on TN1 in the greenhouse. Insecticide sensitivity of the F₂ GLH populations was compared to that of a greenhouse culture that had not been exposed to insecticide treatments. We

used a Burkard microapplicator to apply 0.2 µl each of 5 insecticides, diluted by acetone, on CO₂ anaesthetized 2- to 5-d-old GLH adults.

The LD₅₀ values of the greenhouse population ranged from 0.99 to 8.23; that of field-collected GLH was from 2.40 to 26.47. The estimated resistance ratio